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**TRENDS OF DIETARY HABITS AMONG
MEDICAL STUDENTS**

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ABSTRACT:

Diet is the sum of food consumed by a person or other organism. The word diet often implies the use of specific intake of nutrition for health or weight-management reasons. This cross-sectional study was conducted among medical students of different medical colleges. Name, age, gender, routine, and nature of diet were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. There were 120 medical students in this study. There were 60 males (60%) and 40 females (40%). The mean age of the students was 19.45 ± 0.99 years. Out of 120 medical students, 101 were hostel residents and that they take food from hostel mess. Thirty students said that the hostel mess was not appropriate for them and that they often buy food from outside.

KEYWORD: DIETARY HABITS

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INTRODUCTION:

In nutrition, diet is the sum of food consumed by a person or other organism. The word diet often implies the use of specific intake of nutrition for health or weight-management reasons (with the two often being related). Although humans are omnivores, each culture and each person holds some food preferences or some food taboos. This may be due to personal tastes or ethical reasons. Individual dietary choices may be more or less healthy.

The American Heart Association, World Cancer Research Fund, and American Institute for Cancer Research recommend a diet that consists mostly of unprocessed plant foods, with emphasis on a wide range of whole grains, legumes, and non-starchy vegetables and fruits. This healthy diet includes a wide range of non-starchy vegetables and fruits which provide different colors including red, green, yellow, white, purple, and orange. The recommendations note that tomato cooked with oil, allium vegetables like garlic, and

cruciferous vegetables like cauliflower, provide some protection against cancer. This healthy diet is low in energy density, which may protect against weight gain and associated diseases. Finally, limiting consumption of sugary drinks, limiting energy rich foods, including “fast foods” and red meat, and avoiding processed meats improves health and longevity. Overall, researchers and medical policy conclude that this healthy diet can reduce the risk of chronic disease and cancer.

It is recommended that children consume less than 25 grams of added sugar (100 calories) per day. Other recommendations include no extra sugars in those under 2 years old and less than one soft drink per week. As of 2017, decreasing total fat is no longer recommended, but instead, the recommendation to lower risk of cardiovascular disease is to increase consumption of monounsaturated fats and polyunsaturated fats, while decreasing consumption of saturated fats.

In addition to dietary recommendations for the general population, there are many specific diets that have primarily been developed to promote better health in specific population groups, such as people with high blood pressure (such as low sodium diets or the more specific DASH diet), or people who are overweight or obese (weight control diets). However, some of them may have more or less evidence for beneficial effects in normal people as well (1-3). The objective of this study is to see the trends of dietary habits among medical students.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted among medical students of different medical colleges. Name, age, gender, routine and nature of diet were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

There were 120 medical students in this study. There were 60 males (60%) and 40 females (40%). The mean age of the students was 19.45 ± 0.99 years. Out of 120 medical students, 101 were hostel residents and that they take food from hostel mess. Thirty students said that the hostel mess was not appropriate for them and that they often buy food from outside.

DISCUSSION:

Fears of high cholesterol were frequently voiced up until the mid-1990s. However, more recent research has shown that the distinction between high- and low-density lipoprotein ('good' and 'bad' cholesterol, respectively) must be addressed when speaking of the potential ill effects of cholesterol. Different types of dietary fat have different effects on blood levels of cholesterol. For example, polyunsaturated fats tend to decrease both types of cholesterol; monounsaturated fats tend to lower LDL and raise HDL; saturated fats tend to either raise HDL, or raise

both HDL and LDL; and trans fat tend to raise LDL and lower HDL. Dietary cholesterol is only found in animal products such as meat, eggs, and dairy. The effect of dietary cholesterol on blood cholesterol levels is controversial. Some studies have found a link between cholesterol consumption and serum cholesterol levels. Other studies have not found a link between eating cholesterol and blood levels of cholesterol.

Vending machines in particular have come under fire as being avenues of entry into schools for junk food promoters. However, there is little in the way of regulation and it is difficult for most people to properly analyze the real merits of a company referring to itself as "healthy." Recently, the Committee of Advertising Practice in the United Kingdom launched a proposal to limit media advertising for food and soft drink products high in fat, salt or sugar. The British Heart Foundation released its own government-funded advertisements, labeled "Food4Thought", which were

targeted at children and adults to discourage unhealthy habits of consuming junk food.

From a psychological and cultural perspective, a healthier diet may be difficult to achieve for people with poor eating habits. This may be due to tastes acquired in childhood and preferences for sugary, salty and fatty foods. The UK chief medical officer recommended in December 2018 that sugar and salt be taxed to discourage consumption. The UK government 2020 Obesity Strategy encourages healthier choices by restricting point-of-sale promotions of less-healthy foods and drinks (4-6)

REFERENCES:

1. Hopkins, P. N. (22 March 2016). "Effects of dietary cholesterol on serum cholesterol: a meta-analysis and review". *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*. 55 (6): 1060–70. doi:10.1093/ajcn/55.6.1060. PMID 1534437. S2CID 4452674.
2. "Part D. Chapter 1: Food and Nutrient Intakes, and Health: Current Status and Trends - Continued". Office of Disease Prevention and Health Promotion. Archived from the original on January 11, 2016. Retrieved September 18, 2018.

3. "Launch of public consultation on new food ad rules". Committee of Advertising Practice. 2016. Retrieved 16 August 2016.
4. "British Heart Foundation launches Food4Thought campaign". British Cardiovascular Society. 22 September 2006. Retrieved 16 August 2016.
5. "Told to Eat Its Vegetables, America Orders Fries" article by Kim Severson in The New York Times September 24, 2010, accessed September 25, 2010
6. James WP (2008). "The fundamental drivers of the obesity epidemic". *Obesity Research*. 9 Suppl 1 (Mar, 9 Suppl 1:6-13): 6-13. doi:10.1111/j.1467-789X.2007.00432.x. PMID 18307693. S2CID 19894128.